

School Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction Among Selected School Head in Bongao Island of Tawi-Tawi: A Correlational Study

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Abstract:

This study examines the organizational climate and jobs satisfaction of selected elementary teachers in Bongao island of Tawi-Tawi. Relationship of the school head profile, to the school organizational climate and job satisfaction was also examined. Using descriptive correlational case study design, the investigation was participated by 50 school heads that were purposively selected through convenient sampling. The results of the statistical analysis revealed that most school head claimed to have favorable organizational climate that is friendly warming and transparent. Likewise, most of them also claimed that they are satisfied with their job. However, despite of it

they still said that there is a need to enhance their organizational climate to make them more satisfied to their job, and at the same more support from the government is needed for them to have a self-fulfilling job. On the other hand, findings also revealed that the profile such as age, gender, educational attainment and salary positively influence their organizational climate and job satisfaction. The relationship was highly significant, and their opinions significantly differed. Equally, organizational climate highly influences their job satisfaction and their relationship is directly proportional. As such, organizational leaders, employees/teachers profile has significant bearing in promoting favorable organizational climate while organizational climate has significant contributions in promoting the job satisfaction of the workers.

Keywords: *teachers, school organizational climate, job satisfaction, Bongao-Tawi Tawi.*

Introduction

Organizational climate and job satisfaction is vital for any organization for the employees to become more motivated on their works. Employees who have inspiring working environment, more competitive compensation are productive and satisfied with their job. Each organization has organizational climate which mostly influence by the personality of a person. Organizational climate is the study of perceptions that individual workers or members opined of their working environment (Owens, and Valesky, 2015). According to McLaughlin (2017), organizational climate has many different

types and can be group in varied ways. He said that the climate of an organization could be people oriented, rule-oriented, innovation-oriented or goal-oriented. Organizational climate contributes the success of an organization and job satisfaction of its employees. Organizational climate includes the structures and behavior of leaders and employees. It describes the characteristics of an organizational unit, and affects the attitudes and behaviors of the members (Miner, 2015).

Research conducted by Kumar and Giri (2007) and Lok et.al. (2017) stressed out that organizational climate and job satisfaction plays

vital role towards organization success, affects motivation, performance, and job satisfaction (Davis, 2011). Issues about organizational climate continue to cause employees job dissatisfaction. Gupta (2008) said that more encouraging organizational climate develops prospective and proficient employees. To do this, the organizational leaders should be responsible in building positive and motivate their employees. Leaders believed that when the employees are satisfied with their working environment their performance is at higher level and more committed to do their work. Furthermore, the existence of open communication, management recognition of employees, giving rewards and benefits are most important factors to consider in an organization. Employees will be fully engaged to their work and contented with their job if they are gratified with their working environment (People Insight, 2016). The success of a leaders is not due to worker achievements, but by his responsibility to develop an environment that allows future development and with good relationship with each other (Owen and Valesky, 2015). Teachers commitment is influenced by the leadership of the school (Avey, Palansk & Walumbwa, 2011). Research findings of Wang (2010) revealed that organizational commitment and climate has a positive influence to teacher's job performance.

Various researchers have conducted the same study examining the impact of organizational climate to teacher's performance found out that organizational climate and teacher performance were positively and significantly correlated (Raza and Shah, 2010), organizational climate has considerable impact on teacher commitment (Danish, Daraz, and Ali, 2015), school climate is correlated positively with teacher commitment (Collie, Shapka and Perry, 2011 and Najeemah's, 2012). Considering that most recent studies about the impact of organizational climate to job satisfaction are mostly in foreign countries, this current study focuses on identifying the organizational climate and job satisfaction of

selected school heads in Bongao Tawi-Tawi, island examining their perceived organizational school climate and their job satisfactions explicitly evaluated the extent relation and differences of their perceptions on the following ground;

1. Perceptions of school heads to their organizational school climate
2. School heads self-evaluation on their job satisfaction
3. Relationship between the selected profile, organizational school climate and job satisfaction as perceived by the school heads; and
4. Differences on the perceptions of the school heads regarding organizational climate and job satisfaction

Methods

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational case study design as it tries to find out the type of relationship between respondents' profile, organizational climate and job satisfaction, using survey questionnaires. Quantitative data were gathered through Likert scale type of questionnaire. The participants were also asking to provide comments and suggestions as they perceived that could enhance their job satisfaction and organizational climate of the school. The information given by them were quoted in the discussion as qualitative excerpts.

Research Local and Participants

Research locale of the study was confined only in the mainland of Bongao Tawi-Tawi who involving the 50 school heads who voluntarily participated and answered the survey questionnaire. Convenient sampling was employed in letting the respondents to answer the survey questionnaire.

Table 1. Profile of the School Head Participants

		Frequency	Percent
Age	25-30 yrs old	6	12.0
	31-35 yrs old	4	8.0
	36-40 yrs old	10	20.0
	41-45 yrs old	10	20.0
	46 and above yrs old	20	40.0
Gender	Male	19	38.0
	Female	31	62.0
Education	BSE/BEED	38	76.0
	With Master	9	18.0
	Masters Grad	3	6.0
Monthly salary in peso	Below 20,000	1	2.0
	21,000 -30,000	40	80.0
	31,000 – 40,000	3	6.0
	41,000 – 50,000	6	12.0

Research Instruments

The research instruments used in the study were categorized into four sub-topics. Sub-topic 1 is the personal profile of the participants, sub-topic 2 is the organizational climate survey, the sub-topic 3 is the job satisfaction survey, and the sub-topic 4 is a free entry for their suggestions. The organizational climate and job satisfaction survey was patterned from research instruments used by other researchers who conducted similar study which was modified and validated by the researchers in this study.

Data Analysis

The data obtained from the respondents was quantitatively analyze using descriptive, correlational and analysis of variance. Qualitative data were used to support the discussion.

Results and Discussions

School Heads Perceptions of Their Organizational School Climate

Figure 1 presents school heads personal views about their school organizational climate. As shown in the figure, majority of them claimed that always and occasionally they have a very good organizational climate in school. The perceptions of the school heads show very minimal variation since it has a standard deviation of 0.58 indicating that the values tend to be close to the mean. This finding implies that

the respondents love their working environment and has good relationships to their school principal, peers and students as well (See appendix 1 for details of their perceptions per item).

Figure 1. Organizational Climate as Perceived by the Teachers

Note: Overall mean: 1.5400; standards deviation 0.57888

According to the school heads essay, they usually have benevolent relationship with their immediate supervisor, and teachers, but sometimes strictness also exists. They also said;

“the management in our school or areas is good but it is still needed certain part to change such as in terms of employment”, and we are lucky to have a kind and reliable school head/principal.

However, in some other units, they express that

“our school is lacking with communications and cooperation’s”.

Well, there is really no perfect school organizational climate, and to enhance their working environment, excerpt below were their common suggestions during interview;

- 1) Everybody must have good care and protection the entire school environment.
- 2) Transparency, rest and recreation, bonding.
- 3) Increase the MOOE so that we can improve the school building.
- 4) Open communication between and among superiors and subordinates.
- 5) The leaders or the superiors in the organization should monitor and evaluate the school so that they know the needed things.
- 6) Show openness. transparency, recognition, regular meeting and updates, strengthen communication system.
- 7) My suggestion is to give equal rights in terms of distribution of learning materials and teaching.
- 8) Establish fair treatment, promote unity.
- 9) Assigned most qualified and reliable authority/ head with excellent management skills in serving and instructing his/her subordinates.
- 10) Cooperate and communicate with others so that it continually improving with new ideas.

It is very imperative that employees/teachers are involve in seeking solutions by giving them chance to talk and make propositions and suggestions (People Insight, 2016). According to the study of Gonzalez-Rom’a et al. (2002) the deeper the communication is the better the organizational climate. Others also believed that a more consistent and symbiotic organization promote an encouraging and motivating organizational climate (Zohar & Tenne-Gazit 2008; Luria 2008). This means that to promote good organizational climate in any organization there should be more interdependent, open

communication, more interaction, and clear strategic vision for the job or work.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction refers to an employee's pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from one's job or job experience (Weiss, and Merlo, 2015). Figure 2 shows the job satisfaction of the selected school heads in Bonggao Tawi-Tawi. As shown in the figure, many of them are satisfied with their job considering they indicated always and or occasionally in all items about job satisfaction (See appendix 2 job satisfaction survey). Looking into the small value of standard deviation ($sd = 0.638$) it indicated that their perceived opinions were closed and have a relatively very low variation which means the values tend to be close to the mean

Figure 2. Job satisfaction of the teachers

Note: Overall mean = 1.60;
standard deviation 0.638

Based on their comments and suggestions in the open or free writing aspect in the survey questionnaire, they stated the following as factors that affect their job satisfaction;

- 1) Working environment, and co-workers, communication gaps, and underappreciated.
- 2) Time management, electricity, internet access, lack of training especially in reading and comprehension, educational technology.

- 3) Misunderstanding with coworkers, unequal treatment of superior to his/her personnel.
- 4) Lack of support sometimes, and inspiration by leaders and subordinate.
- 5) Lack of information, because of the distance since we are in an island.
- 6) Lack of school buildings and teachers.
- 7) Unfair treatment of superiors, delinquent co-workers
- 8) Lack of school facilities and related learning materials, also some other personal reasons such as salary that cannot augment in our daily expenses.

Likewise, they also posed the following suggestions to enhance their job satisfaction;

- 1) Change the working environment, by providing internet connection, improve school facilities and provision of learning modalities.
- 2) More productive activities or seminars that are related to our job, attend more educational seminars and trainings.
- 3) Provide additional teachers and school building, and access road repair.
- 4) Transparent and close contact with co-workers, showing warmth to everyone.
- 5) Having good relationship with co-workers and superiors.
- 6) The superiors or head of organization should monitor and evaluate the system or management properly and improve it competitively.
- 7) Good leadership.
- 8) Fair treatment, friendly environment, and good relationship with co-employees.

According to Flynn (2022), job satisfaction promotes more opportunity, healthy environment and appreciation. When an employee is satisfied with their job they will perform effectively and efficiently. Studies have shown that job commitment is an indicator of satisfaction, and job satisfaction is a product of organizational climate. Enhancing job

satisfaction will create a supportive environment and enhance job commitment (Alomian, 2010). Likewise, Chin and Rowley (2018) said that job satisfaction promotes employee well-being and psychological health. It is also an indicator for numerous desirable organizational outcomes and employee behavior. This means that identifying employees job satisfaction is very crucial for an organization to determine its current management, supervision and leadership.

Relationship between Participants Profile, Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction

Findings presented in Table 2 revealed that the profile of the school heads such as age, gender, education and salary is positively associated to their organizational climate and job satisfaction. The correlation shows that their relationship is highly significant since the significant value of each construct is lower than the critical value $\alpha=0.05$. Similarly, organizational climate is also positively correlated to job satisfaction and their relationship is highly significant. The direct and positive relationship between these variables implies that when the working environment and the organizational climate is very conducive and friendly, it makes the employees or workers more satisfied to their job, this also holds true to their age, gender, education and salary since these have a positive bearing towards organizational climate and job satisfaction. The results show that the higher the educational attainment, and salary the more they are concerned with their organizational climate and job satisfaction. It follows that, higher qualifications demand higher salary so they are more or less satisfied with their job and the organizational climate once these things are satisfied. The research conducted by Wang (2010) concluded that school climate enhances the level of teachers' commitment, and it has a positive influence to job satisfaction and performance.

Based on this finding, it affirms that organizational climate, and job satisfaction will matter with respect to the personal profile of the employees or teachers. Study conducted by Liao & Chuang (2007) and Walumbwa et al. (2010) pointed out that leadership is very important in

organizational climate. Similarly, leader's personal profile and characteristics are very important in any organization as well (Salvaggio et. al, 2007). The quality of the organizational head and employees has significant contribution in promoting good organizational climate that lead to their efficient working performance (Chuang & Liao, 2010). A significant correlation was evident between organizational climate, job stress, workplace burnout, and retention (Lan, Huang Kao, and Wang, 2020).

Research findings of Jyotil (2013) revealed that educational level and experiences has significant effects on organizational climate. Leaders and employees/teachers who had high educational attainment and experience have more positive perceptions in developing good and conducive organizational climate. Jyotil (2013) concluded in his research that organizational climate and job satisfaction are vital in holding efficient employees/teachers and the same time enhances

their commitment to their work. In wider perspective, environment where employees are satisfied with their job can fully engage their work and encouraging organizational climate promote the organization ability to attract, retain and develop the employees/teachers skills and talents (People Insight, 2016). Working environment as regards to organizational climate and employees/teachers working experiences is difficult to assess but it directs their daily lives. Thus, organizational climate is also affected by other factors which include the organizational culture (Schneider, B.; Ehrhart, M.G.; and Macey, W.H. (2013). Organizational climate has a strong influence to job satisfaction and influence employees attitudes and feelings (Prastiawan, 2020). Organizational culture. Thus, in an environment with high job stress, institutions must create a favorable organizational climate to strengthen employees' positive perceptions and effectively reduce their intention to leave.

Table 2. Correlation between Participants Profile, Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction

Spearman's rho		Organizational Climate	Job satisfaction
AGE	Correlation Coefficient	.861**	.858**
	Sig. (2-tailed) value	.000	.000
GENDER	Correlation Coefficient	.769**	.787**
	Sig. (2-tailed) value	.000	.000
EDUCATION	Correlation Coefficient	.504**	.486**
	Sig. (2-tailed) value	.000	.000
SALARY	Correlation Coefficient	.436**	.432**
	Sig. (2-tailed) value	.002	.002
JOB SATISFACTION	Correlation Coefficient	.950**	
	Sig. (2-tailed) value	.000	

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Differences on the Perceptions of the School Heads as to Their Profile

Table 3 to table 6 shows the analysis of variance to determine if there is a significant difference on the perceptions of the school heads about their organizational climate and job satisfaction as to their profile. As shown in Table 3, there is no significant difference between their salary and their perceived organizational climate (OC), but it significantly differed with regards to their job

satisfaction (p value $.046 < \alpha=0.05$). However, both the perceived organizational climate and job satisfaction significantly differ with respect to their education as shown in Table 4 (p value $.005$ and $.006 < \alpha=0.05$). This means that their perceptions vary as to their level of education. It is also true since education significantly influence organizational climate and job satisfaction (Table 2). Similarly, school heads perceptions on organizational climate and job

satisfaction shows significant differences with respect to their gender and age as shown in Table

5 and 6 considering that the p value computed is lower than $\alpha=0.05$.

Table 3. ANOVA Table for Salary vs Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction

	SALARY	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p value)	Analysis
OC	Between Groups	2.520	.840	2.780	.052	No significant difference
	Within Groups	13.900	.302			
JS	Between Groups	3.167	1.056	2.884	.046	Has significant difference
	Within Groups	16.833	.366			

Note: OC = Organizational Climate; JS = Job Satisfaction

Table 4. ANOVA Table for Education vs Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction

	EDUCATION	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p value)	Analysis
OC	Between Groups	3.341	1.671	6.003	.005	Has significant difference
	Within Groups	13.079	.278			
JS	Between Groups	3.939	1.969	5.763	.006	Has significant difference
	Within Groups	16.061	.342			

Note: OC = Organizational Climate; JS = Job Satisfaction

Table 5. ANOVA Table for Gender vs Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction

	GENDER	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p value)	Analysis
OC	Between Groups	8.936	8.936	57.314	.000	Has significant difference
	Within Groups	7.484	.156			
JS	Between Groups	11.032	11.032	59.050	.000	Has significant difference
	Within Groups	8.968	.187			

Note: OC = Organizational Climate; JS = Job Satisfaction

Table 6. ANOVA Table for Age vs Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction

	AGE	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p value)	Analysis
OC	Between Groups	12.120	3.030	31.709	.000	Has significant difference
	Within Groups	4.300	.096			
JS	Between Groups	14.400	3.600	28.929	.000	Has significant difference
	Within Groups	5.600	.124			

Note: OC = Organizational Climate; JS = Job Satisfaction

According to the study of Khan (2019), developing a positive organizational climate will improve teacher commitment. Thus, teachers need to know the importance of organizational climate to ensure their commitments. Educational leaders like school principal should develop a healthy and positive organizational climate for teachers to ensure their job

satisfaction. Since organizational climate has many different types, (McLaughlin, 2017), then school leaders should address an organizational climate in varied ways. Many research findings revealed that educational level and experiences significantly affects organizational climate and job satisfaction (Jyotil, 2013; People Insight, 2016), and plays vital role towards organizational

success (Kumar and Giri (2007) and Lok et.al. (2017).

Conclusion

Base on the purpose of the study that to evaluate the school heads perceived organizational climate and job satisfaction, as well as the extent relationship of organizational climate job satisfaction and their profile. From the findings, most school heads claimed to have favorable organizational climate that is friendly warming and transparent, and that they were satisfied with their job. Despite of their satisfaction and good working environment they still suggested to enhance their organizational climate to make them more satisfied to their job, and at the same more support from the government is needed for them to have a self-fulfilling job. It is also notable that personal profile such as age, gender, educational attainment, and salary plays significant contribution in developing good organizational climate and job satisfaction. Similarly, organizational climate is tangible in the job satisfaction of employees. Therefore, when organizational climate and working environment is conducive and favorable to the workers, then they tend to be satisfied with their job. Thus, it is very important to note that organizational leaders must be sensitive and vigilant with the existing organizational climate in their organization. They must be a game player that motivate and enhance the employees to be more productive and happier to their work and environment.

Limitation and Recommendation

The study has a very limited number of respondents at hand due to geographic location of the island. Furthermore, the variables investigated was limited only on some selected profiles which can be modified for further research. Thus, it is recommended that research with larger samples and more variables to be captured is necessary to explore whether the relationships we found could be generalized to other public or private schools across the country. Additional new assessment scales are

also encouraged or adapt a widely-used assessment scale. From the findings of the study, it is notable that a friendly organizational climate promote job satisfaction thus, it is also recommended that school administrators should establish and maintained favorable school organizational climate to the teachers and this is applicable to all other organization as well to improved teacher commitment to ensure overall success.

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Appendix 1.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Teachers response on Organizational Climate

Statement		Always		Occasionally		Seldom		Never	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1	I always receive the information that is needed to do my job	20	40	28	56	2	4	0	
2	I believe that I will have career growth opportunities in this school	20	40	27	54	3	6	0	
3	I am encouraged to contribute to the improvement of work processes	23	46	26	52	1	2	0	
4	I always learn new things in my job	26	52	21	42	3	6	0	
5	Clarification and guidance from my superiors regarding my tasks help me carry out my work	25	50	21	42	4	8	0	
6	My superiors help me to figure out how to learn and train	21	42	25	50	4	8	0	
7	The school provide training opportunities for everyone	17	34	23	46	9	18	1	2
8	The school have career outlook that motivates me to work for this school	17	34	28	56	5	10	0	
9	The organization's environment facilitates the relationship between employees	24	48	22	44	4	8	0	
10	My colleagues always willing to help each another	30	60	19	38	1	2	0	
11	I trust my co-workers	28	56	19	38	3	6	0	
12	The employees of this school have a good relationship with each other	28	56	19	38	3	6	0	
13	The school administrators come promptly when I need their help	21	42	24	48	5	10	0	
14	When I have finished my work day and go home, I feel fulfilled Professionally	25	50	23	46	2	4	0	
15	The employees are involved in decision making	23	46	24	48	3	6	0	
16	I believe that the time I use in my work day is sufficient to fulfil my duties and obligations	20	40	28	56	2	4	0	
17	I wish I had more senior responsibilities	20	40	25	50	5	10	0	
18	I am happy in my work	30	60	18	36	2	4	0	
19	I consider that my work is important for the school to reach its goals	37	74	11	22	2	4	0	
20	I feel that working in this school contributes to improving my life	29	58	19	38	2	4	0	

Appendix 2.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Teachers response on Job satisfaction

Statement		Always		Occasionally		Seldom		Never
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f
1	Are you satisfied with your school's culture?	20	40	23	46	7	14	0
2	Are you satisfied with your job and make your work meaningful?	27	54	21	42	2	4	0
3	Is your school give you chances for your professional growth and promotion?	18	36	26	52	6	12	0
4	Do you feel valued for your contributions?	22	44	25	50	3	6	0
5	Does your school provide instructional materials and facilities needed for your teaching?	16	32	26	52	8	16	0
6	Do your supervisor and principal transparent in communication?	20	40	26	52	4	8	0
7	Do you think that time management and distribution in teaching loads are balance?	20	40	25	50	5	10	0
8	Do you feel connected to your co-workers?	30	60	18	36	2	4	0
9	Do you feel your significance in the school?	27	54	21	42	2	4	0
10	Do the school heads and management promote unity and camaraderie?	30	60	18	36	2	4	0